

BPMN4Earth: Metadata Enriched & Automated Workflows

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Abstract

The comprehensibility, explanatory power, replicability, and reusability of research data are highly dependent on the description of workflows, but currently there is no common standardized format for workflow documentation in the Earth System Sciences that is human- and machine-readable. We propose the usage of the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) framework to describe workflows, capture workflow-related metadata, and automate processes. We have investigated different BPMN frameworks, implemented a command line application as a proof-of-concept that covers the fundamental requirements, and tested it with workflows from field- and laboratory environments.

The concept has been evaluated positively and will be implemented in our laboratories. Additionally, the results are going to be implemented in follow-up projects like the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration project Sematic x-Lab.

¹ Based on the CRediT Contributor Roles Taxonomy: <https://credit.niso.org/>

I. Introduction

In the Earth System Science (ESS) domain, we are confronted with an ever-growing amount of (meta-) data from samples, observations/measurements, and analyses. Specifically, the demand for high resolution spatial and temporal data is leading to an increase in laboratory workload which necessitates simultaneous improvements in processing capacities by means of digitalization and automation. Moreover, data quality with regards to comprehensibility, explanatory power, replicability, and reusability is highly dependent on the detailed description of laboratory workflows², namely, the documentation of:

- i. sample preparation methods (e.g., which processing steps have been applied to a sample),
- ii. instruments and settings (e.g., persistent identifiers (PID) for instruments, sampling frequency, reference standard, temperature profile, injection-volume), and
- iii. subsequent data processing (e.g., calibration, evaluation, aggregation, visualization).

In some cases, workflow descriptions might only be passed on verbally during on-boarding/training (e.g., when they are considered trivial), but often they are stored as combinations of analogue lab notebooks, text/spreadsheet documents, collaboratively edited markdown notes (e.g., HedgeDoc), hypertext documents (e.g., DokuWiki, MediaWiki), and in electronic lab notebooks (ELN) or laboratory infrastructure systems (LIMS), respectively (e.g., Medusa, mDIS, Chemotion, openBIS, Senaite).

Therefore, we are not only confronted with a tremendous amount of different ESS workflows, but the available data and metadata vary widely with respect to structure, format, level of detail, usage of terminologies/ontologies, findability, accessibility, etc. Wikis, for instance, are easily accessible and offer a lot of flexibility, but are neither suitable for publications nor machine-actionable. ELNs on the other hand tend to have a narrow scope while ESS research requires a wide range of sample types (e.g., rock, sediment, soil, water, plant material, microorganisms) and analytical methods (e.g., grain size measurements, stable isotope and biomarker analyses, cosmogenic nuclide dating, water chemistry).

Specifically in ESS, we also experience discontinuities between field and laboratory work, because user requirements and data types differ significantly between both settings. Domain-/community specific electronic field notebooks (EFN) might be preferentially used in a field-setting instead of ELNs, but the necessary data transfer between systems is likely to pose issues due to the reliance on specific platforms/operating systems, a lack of exchange formats or application programming interfaces (API), etc. And finally, the nature of activities in workflows is manifold. In the broadest sense, we distinguish between:

- i. manual tasks (e.g., setting up a broadband seismometer, taking a sediment core, packing a column for chromatography),
- ii. hybrid tasks (e.g., transferring analogue data into a webform, configuring a sensor), and
- iii. digital tasks (e.g., archiving data, calculating a calibration curve, training a neural network).

² For reasons of clarity and comprehensibility, we will often use the term workflow or method description instead of process, although the latter is typically used in the domain of business process modeling. The term business is synonymous with ESS in this context, including adjacent areas such as administration and management.

Taking all these issues into account, we proposed an alternative approach that relies on the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) framework. BPMN is an internationally established, well documented, and widely used standard for process modeling (Object Management Group 2013, and International Organization for Standardization 2013). Because BPMN is a generic, but very expressive and flexible tool, we argue that it can describe most of the – if not the complete – research data lifecycle including field and laboratory work. BPMN, and this is crucial to understand, comprises models on the one hand, and instances of these models on the other hand.

a) BPMN Models

A process model is a directed graph that defines the structure and logic of a business process (e.g., standard operating procedures (SOP)), outlining all pathways and decision points. It serves as a blueprint for how a process can unfold. A detailed BPMN model might include some metadata (e.g., a PID for the model, identifiers from the Research Organization Registry ([ROR](#)), PIDs for instruments from a specific laboratory, default settings for measuring equipment), but it does not contain data. A well-conceived model will also include error handling for common issues (e.g., delivery problems with consumables, malfunctions of crucial devices, unavailability of network-/web services) to prevent gridlocks.

Depending on the complexity of a process the initial amount of work involved with the creation of a model can be very high, but costs for additions, updates and upgrades subsequently decrease, because (parts of) existing models can be reused. However, cost reductions have a limit, as overall complexity and maintenance expenses – such as those for bug fixes and software updates – tend to rise simultaneously.

b) Model Instances

Each time we execute a model (e.g., deploy a gauging station, process a batch of samples in a laboratory), we create a new, independent instance. In contrast to the model, an instance contains only the pathway that was actually realized and the (meta-) data that are associated with it (e.g., a research activity identifier ([RAiD](#)), Open Researcher and Contributor IDs ([ORCID](#)), International Generic Sample Numbers ([IGSN](#)), a cost center, sample weights/volumes/concentrations). Due to the reduction in complexity, instances can be represented by – and stored as ordinary sequences.

The more instances are created, the better the cost-benefit-ratio for the underlying model.

II. Results

Applying the BPMN approach to ESS research helps to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). In the following, a workflow that describes surface exposure dating based on cosmogenic nuclides (Beryllium-10) will serve as an example. In its entirety the workflow includes field campaigns to South America and Central Asia for rock sample collection, complex laboratory work at GFZ in Potsdam, a measurement procedure at the accelerated mass spectrometer in Cologne (CologneAMS), statistical evaluation of the measurement results and their geochronological interpretation (Figure 1). Because BPMN is a hierarchical modeling

language, the depicted workflow could be part of a more extensive workflow that includes application for funding, sampling strategy, data management planning, etc.

Figure 1: High level overview of a workflow modeled in BPMN. Circles represent events, rounded corner rectangles are activities, and the sequence flow is indicated by arrows. Plus-symbols mark activities as compound activities (“subprocess”).

a) Implemented Solution

i) Framework

The fundamental technical components of a BPMN frameworks are i) an editor for modeling, and ii) a process engine to generate instances. Commercial applications like Camunda or SAP Signavio are usually marketed as software as a service (SaaS) and add valuable features like graphical user interfaces (GUI), user and project management, process and performance monitoring, version control, form generators, terminology services, etc. In the context of this pilot, there were considerable downsides for SaaS offerings though, which require mid- to long-term strategic decisions (e.g., additional complexity, proprietary components, potential vendor lock-in, data security concerns, associated costs, integration into existing IT infrastructure).

Therefore, we showcase the applicability of the approach using the open-source project SpiffWorkflow (Esswein et al., 2025). The SpiffWorkflow community uses an editor that is based on the bpmn.io project and has implemented a process engine with very few dependencies in Python. Although open-source, free to use, platform-independent, very inclusive, and responsive to feedback and requests, we still need to be aware that both projects are backed by for-profit companies: bpmn.io is maintained by Camunda and SpiffWorkflow by Sartography.

ii) Editor

BPMN’s ability to be rendered both as a visual diagram and as a machine-readable language is one of its greatest strengths, and the editor serves to fully leverage this dual nature. BPMN is based on the Extensible Markup Language (XML) which stores information in plain text files that are usually encoded in UTF-8. The format is machine-actionable and can be versioned, but reading and editing with a generic text editor requires expert knowledge and is prone to error (Figure 2).

The shown BPMN example is part of the sample preparation in the GFZ laboratories and describes the separation of magnetic and non-magnetic minerals/particles. The task is executed with an analogue magnetic separator and the samples need to be fed through the machine twice using different settings for inclination and magnetic field intensity (expressed as electrical current). To avoid (code) duplication in our BPMN model, we combine all necessary steps for a pass-through within a BPMN subprocess (Figure 2, line 3). When the process engine executes the model, it repeats the subprocess once for each entry in the settings list (Figure 2, lines 15 to 19) which is initialized at the start of the subprocess in the preScript-element (Figure 2, lines 6 to 12).

```
1 <bpmn:definitions ... xmlns:spiffworkflow="http://spiffworkflow.org/bpmn/schema/1.0/core" ...>
2   ...
3   <bpmn:subProcess id="..." name="Separate magnetic particles">
4     ...
5     <bpmn:extensionElements>
6       <spiffworkflow:preScript>
7         settings = [
8           {"inclination [deg]": 12.0, "current [A]": 0.5},
9           {"inclination [deg]": 7.0, "current [A]": 2.0},
10          ]
11         i = -1
12       </spiffworkflow:preScript>
13     </bpmn:extensionElements>
14     ...
15     <bpmn:standardLoopCharacteristics>
16       <bpmn:loopCondition xsi:type="bpmn:tFormalExpression">
17         i == len(settings) - 1
18       </bpmn:loopCondition>
19     </bpmn:standardLoopCharacteristics>
20     ...
21   </bpmn:subProcess>
22   ...
23 </bpmn:definitions>
```

Figure 2: BPMN models are defined in XML files that can be displayed by any text editor. In line 1, a XML namespace called “spiffworkflow” is declared through an uniform resource identifier (URI). The namespace contains extensions to the BPMN standard like the preScript-element in lines 6 to 12 that is used to declare Python variables for SpiffWorkflow’s process engine.

As a result, changes of the settings or the number of pass-throughs do not require structural changes to the workflow, but a modification of the settings list.

Including default settings into a model is very straightforward, but might not necessarily be the best approach for all situations. Alternatively, a Python script can be included or called that reads the required parameters from separate files, or fetches them through an API call (e.g., from the Sensor Management System ([SMS](#)) (Brinckmann et al. 2025)).

In contrast to a text editor, a BPMN editor provides an intuitive, easy to handle, graphical representation of models, and seamlessly integrates non-standardized features (Figure 3). These additions are framework specific though which will cause issues when switching between different implementations. While XML tags unambiguously signal which elements are extensions, the graphical representation blurs the difference.

The breadcrumbs navigation in the upper left of Figure 3 indicates another core feature of BPMN: process hierarchies. The top-level workflow in this example is called “CosmoLab” (short for cosmogenic nuclide laboratory). It contains a subprocess that describes “Physical preprocessing” which in turn contains the depicted workflow to remove magnetic particles. This nesting greatly improves clarity, because it reduces the cognitive load for the user and enables us to communicate at a level of detail that is appropriate for the audience: For a peer reviewer it might be sufficient to know that magnetic particles have been removed in the workflow, but a lab assistant needs to know exactly which steps to perform.

Figure 3: Graphical editors provide users with low-code access to BPMN models. The selected element (highlighted with a blue outline) is the same as shown in Figure 2. It is adorned with shortcuts to connect it with additional BPMN elements, change properties, etc.

Subprocesses are contained in the same file as the rest of the model. If a subprocess is supposed to be (re-)used in multiple workflows, it is modeled as an independent process, i.e. file, which is then referenced in a “call activity”.

iii) Process Engine

The second base component of a BPMN framework is the process engine. It executes and orchestrates processes that have been modeled with BPMN and is responsible for API calls as well as the serialization of instances, i.e., the translation of workflow data into a state that can be stored in and read from files or databases.

Unlike most process engines, SpiffWorkflow is implemented in Python which is widely used in the ESS domain. It presents us with two different options for the user interface: The first is a relatively simple offline application that uses a few additional libraries to create a command line interface (CLI), while the second is a fully featured web application with a GUI that runs front- and backend components in isolated docker containers (SpiffArena). Given our scientific backgrounds and our resources for this pilot, we opted for the less complex option, although the GUI version is much closer to the original proposal (see Chapter III). Regardless of the decision, the workflows we modeled and the input masks they use, are fully compatible between both interface options.

The CLI application in its current form includes all fundamental operations like registering, selecting and executing workflows, saving progress and metadata to files or a SQLite database, switching between running workflows, etc. It has very low hardware and software requirements

and can be installed on every system that supports Python, even single-board computers like a Raspberry Pi.

Figure 4 shows the execution of the example workflow within the CLI application. The user has stepped into the previously described subprocess to separate magnetic particles and is now presented with the tasks that it contains. The workflow engine infers possible states for each task of the process model and distinguishes between predicted (possible), definite and finished tasks. Here, all tasks are marked as “ready”, a subcategory of definite, because they are part of a “parallel gateway”. In general, BPMN gateways are means of flow control based on predefined conditions and runtime data (“decisions”). A parallel gateway is a special case that enables concurrency, i.e. users and operators³ are given the flexibility to execute the given tasks the order they prefer.

```

Set the inclination [READY]
Set the current [READY]
Place collection boxes [READY]
Add sample [READY]
Switch on chute and feed vibrations [READY]

Name: Activity_lilsglb
Bpmn ID: Activity_lilsglb
Bpmn name: Set the inclination
Description: Manual Task
Last state change: 2025-03-10 14:35:28.153152

Data
sample_name: "22KG-17"
total_quantity: 634.2
required_quantity: 5
large_chunks: 0
settings: [
  {
    "inclination [deg]": 12.0,
    "current [A]": 0.5
  },
  {
    "inclination [deg]": 7.0,
    "current [A]": 2.0
  }
]
i: 0

[l]ist/tree view [w]orkflow/task data view [g]reedy/step execution [f]ilter tasks [u]pdate waiting tasks [s]ave workflow state

2025-03-10 14:35:28.140714 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Event_lw2g5so) State changed to COMPLETED
2025-03-10 14:35:28.141130 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Activity_lbedve9) State changed to READY
2025-03-10 14:35:28.148553 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Activity_lbedve9) State changed to COMPLETED
2025-03-10 14:35:28.149361 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Gateway_0y01mwq) State changed to READY
2025-03-10 14:35:28.152850 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Gateway_0y01mwq) State changed to COMPLETED
2025-03-10 14:35:28.153184 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Activity_lilsglb) State changed to READY
2025-03-10 14:35:28.153544 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Activity_0deh921) State changed to READY
2025-03-10 14:35:28.153891 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Activity_0n9e9xh) State changed to READY
2025-03-10 14:35:28.154223 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Activity_0zdwegm) State changed to READY
2025-03-10 14:35:28.154570 [spiff.task:INFO] (Activity_lhojlv0:Activity_lmhcagk) State changed to READY
2025-03-10 14:35:45.883891 [spiff_engine:INFO] Saved workflow 29fec55b-82a0-4694-a285-ddfd862474bf

```

Figure 4: The SpiffWorkflow process engine running inside a CLI application. On the upper left, five up-coming tasks from the active subprocess can be selected. On the upper right, metadata that are associated with the instance are listed (e.g., sample name, sample name, sample weight, inclination and current setting). Below, CLI keybindings are listed and logging output including the unique identifier of the instance is displayed (starting with 29fec55b).

³ We use the term “user” to refer to a person who interacts with the application, and the term “operator” for somebody who executes a manual task in the field/lab. Ideally, but not necessarily, both roles are combined in the same person.

Multiple instances of the same workflow can be executed simultaneously (e.g., different field deployments, sample batches, etc.), because individual instances are distinguished by universally unique identifiers (UUID). The user can save the current state of an instance at any point, suspend its execution, and switch to a different workflow instance instead.

The task selected to be executed next (emphasized by bold text) is a “manual task”. It gives the user on-screen instructions to set the inclination of the device based on the content of the settings list and iteration index. The user confirms the execution of the task after they have changed the inclination, and the next task is triggered (Figure 5). In general, when dealing with manual tasks the flow of information goes predominantly from the application to the user informing them what to do. Only the confirmation that the task has been executed is stored with the instance.

Figure 5: Manual tasks do not involve data input or IT components. Their execution is just confirmed.

“User tasks” on the other hand enable the exchange of information through forms in the opposite direction, i.e. from the user to the application (Figure 6). In bpmn.io/SpiffWorkflow, forms are generated using the React JSON Schema Form ([RJSE](https://github.com/bpmn-io/spiff-workflow)) framework which builds on [JSON schema](https://ajv.js.org/) for type definitions (e.g., Boolean, number, string) and input validation (e.g., temperatures must be larger than absolute zero, geographic latitudes range from -90° to $+90^{\circ}$).

Figure 6: User tasks can include forms of arbitrary complexity for data input. In this example the user needs to enter the sample weight in metric grams. The form framework checks the input type (number) and validity (positive value). The unit should be stored with the metadata to avoid ambiguities.

Because the data stored with the instance are constantly being updated, they are also immediately available for decision making at gateways, and automated processing through BPMN’s “script task” and “service task” (Figure 7). In SpiffWorkflow, these tasks are implemented in Python and can be used for virtually everything (e.g., print labels, calculate dilution factors or calibration curves, schedule resources for upcoming tasks, communicate with APIs, clean and synchronize data, update dashboards in web services, (re-)train neural networks). This feature is incredibly powerful, but might also depend on the availability of external interfaces. Especially when inter-acting with proprietary software (e.g., drivers for printers, control software for analytical devices), we often found these interfaces non-existing, lacking/undocumented or inaccessible,

although in some cases partial automation was still possible through interchange formats (e.g., csv, xlsx).

```
Provide HDPE bottles
```

```
Given your 15% estimate of the quartz percentage, you need to start with 34g of sample material at least.
The recommended amount of uncleaned sample per 1-liter-HDPE bottle is 20.0g (the maximum is 40.0g).
```

```
Collect 2 clean bottles from the cupboard.
```

```
Note: Not everyone does a good job at bottle cleaning, so make sure the inside of the bottles has no
grains stuck to the bottom.
```

```
[Done]
```

Figure 7: Script tasks can be used to update instructions. In this case the operator has estimated the quartz percentage of a sample to be 15% in a previous step. Based upon the estimate, the required amount of sample material for the next processing step is calculated (34g), and in combination with prior experiences, the number of reaction vessels to be prepared is returned (2 pcs.). The following steps include suggestions for labeling the vessels (or printing labels) and the ideal amount of material per vessel.

Given that most users are neither familiar nor comfortable with CLI applications the use value to a wider audience is limited. Although we have not dealt extensively with the web-based graphical interface of SpiffArena, Figure 8 gives an impression how a RJSF form is rendered by a web browser. In contrast to the CLI examples from above, the GUI enables rich text editing including the use of links (e.g., to additional documentation, software/data repositories, publications, services that can't be accessed automatically through an API) and visual cues (e.g., screenshots of proprietary control software, pictures of equipment, maps, graphs).

b) Data and Software availability

The SpiffWorkflow engine as well as the editor and the GUI version (SpiffArena) are available at <https://github.com/sartography>. The engine is subject to LGPL-3.0 and SpiffArena to LGPL-2.1 while the editor is available under the MIT license. The repositories link extensive documentation and there is an active and very welcoming community on the Discord social platform.

For BPMN4Earth, we have forked a CLI example from SpiffWorkflow. The original repository had grown over years, but had not been actively maintained for quite some time which resulted in a confusing project layout. We restructured it to our needs and created pull requests for our changes including some bugfixes. However, at that time the maintainers had moved their focus to SpiffArena and were lacking resources to solve merge conflicts. Thus, the majority of our development has not been included in the official repository, but is available as supplement to this report including the exemplary workflow. The only prerequisites for a test run are a working Python and (for the editor) Docker installation.

Spiffworkflow < Process Groups / Examples / 1. Basics / Using Forms / Process Instance Id: 2865 / Task: Simple Form

Task: Simple Form (Using Forms)

This is a simple form with pre-filled default values. All fields are required. The Age range is limited to sane values. You can test out validation by:

1. entering an age of greater than 130, or less than 18.
2. not providing a first name
3. providing a bio that is less than 10 characters long.

First name *

Last name *

Age of person *

Bio *

Submit Save and close

Figure 8: SpiffArena's GUI is accessed through a web browser and thus platform independent. The example is based on the online tutorial and shows menu items on the left and a RJSF form rendered on the right.

c) Innovation and FAIRness

Workflow descriptions contain information about field deployments, laboratory processes, analysis methods, data processing, etc. They are most often published as parts of scientific publications and are therefore subject to a number of limitations (e.g., access barriers, format, concise-ness). The structure and level of detail of the descriptions vary widely, because – even when they are based on SOPs – they are heavily influenced by personal field- and laboratory notes and domain specific mannerisms.

BPMN models on the other hand offer a standardized format that is generic, but very expressive and flexible. BPMN is easy to understand for humans and machine-actionable at the same time. As we have demonstrated above, the level of detail of a model can be adjusted to the audience by means of process hierarchies, and common process steps can be shared between models to avoid unnecessary duplication. The usage of BPMN models can also save the authors from having to compile data and metadata in retrospect as the metadata enrichment happens continuously throughout the workflow. For more details on the issue, please also see chapter IV.

III. Challenges and Gaps

While we made considerable progress with regards to the usage of BPMN in an ESS context, we did not manage to address all working packages from the proposal for a number of different reasons.

Being aware of the technical complexity of the topic and in the light of other successful collaborations, we reached out to GFZ's research software engineers (RSE) in the eScience Centre during the proposal stage of BPMN4Earth. As a result, the timing of the work packages and allocation of resources was aligned with eScience's anticipated availability of capacities.

With regards to the allocation of resources there was a significant uncertainty, though: One of the authors had been offered a permanent position in a different pay grade, but compared to the project duration, the associated administrative process took an excessively long time. Therefore, the amount of RSE support that BPMN4Earth could actually afford in terms of FTEs remained uncertain. By the time the issue was finally settled, we had missed several windows of opportunity, and the eScience Centre had to focus on the evaluation of the Helmholtz DataHub. The evaluation resulted in a shift of priorities at GFZ and in combination with unexpected staff turnover, the eScience Centre finally had to completely withdraw their commitment to BPMN4Earth on short notice.

Independently, we underestimated the time it would take to become acquainted with the necessary technologies that were required for the pilot. In a previous project we had experienced a very low entrance barrier when it came to the usage of graphical BPMN editors. However, when we started looking into metadata enrichment and process engines, we experienced a rather steep learning curve independently of the chosen framework. For the reasons described above, we settled with SpiffWorkflow, but its code base had grown over more than a decade as a collaborative project before it got adopted by Sartography, which made it to some extent unintuitive and convoluted. This, however, also presented us with the opportunity to get in contact with the developers who supported us to the best of their abilities.

Because the project scope touches virtually every bit of the research lifecycle, it was also very hard to keep up with the multitude of applications/services in existence and under development that needed to be potentially considered (e.g., data management (planning), sample management, equipment management, laboratory infrastructure, high performance clusters for computations) for data ingestion and export. Just in our immediate environment, we got involved with the SMS, the laboratory/research infrastructure inventory portal (LI2/RI), GFZ's SampleHub initiative, the Geomorphology section's DataLake project as well as the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration project Semantic x-Lab (Knodel, 2025). Given the fact that some of their representatives were present at one of our presentations, we were surprised though, when we learned that the center administration had started to develop a digital application portal using BPMN later without reaching out to us.

A work package that we did not manage to complete is WP2 ("PIDs for workflows"). Although we had contacted the head of GFZ's former Library and Information Services (LIS, now Data and Information Management), presented our ideas, and discussed available options, we faced a similar problem as with the eScience section when the head of LIS left GFZ unexpectedly. A promising idea to render a separate service for workflow PIDs (at least temporarily) unnecessary, was using GitLab repositories to store workflow models and use commit hashes as PIDs. Then, each instance of the workflow could be captured in a separate fork of the repository. We never actually got to test this approach though, and it is uncertain how much load this would put on a GitLab-server in terms of the number of forks created and their size.

Although the CLI application provides the fundamental operations that are necessary, it is missing crucial features. First and foremost, the application does not support a client-server architecture

and does not have any kind of user management. Not having workflows registered at a central server with granular access control and data backup, but spread over multiple installations is prone to error and very cumbersome.

Another severe downside is the missing integration with the editor which runs in a browser. New workflows and updates of existing workflows need to be registered manually in (every installation of) the CLI application which is – again – prone to errors and cumbersome. Finally, the use of the command line in general has proven to be discouraging to new users, and the rendering of RJSF forms and their validation inside a browser are much more robust.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

Workflow descriptions are an essential part of scientific communication and indispensable for comprehensibility, validation, and replicability of our findings. They supply context to the work and enable the assessment of the quality and reliability of data, results, and interpretations. Workflow descriptions are typically part of the method section in publications and therefore subject to the same access barriers (e.g., discoverability, paywalls). Because journals need to re-strict the number of words or pages per article, workflow descriptions are by design incomplete. This deficiency is partly remedied by references to other publications, but the approach is prone to error, results in knowledge fragmentation, and might have a negative impact on repeatability and replicability⁴.

Moreover, workflow descriptions were historically only meant to be read by human readers. Therefore, they usually consist of textual descriptions and illustrations (e.g., drawings, images, diagrams, charts), which are not machine-actionable (unless we take natural language processing and image analysis into account) which impedes automated knowledge discovery and reuse.

In comparison, BPMN models can be used to describe workflows with an arbitrary level of detail in a standardized format. They are human and machine-readable, and can be executed along the way during field- and lab work to capture all metadata that are considered meaningful. Due to the standardized format, models and instances are more likely to be comparable, even more so when well-defined vocabularies are used. Furthermore, because data are linked to specific workflows and their metadata, they become easier to discover (e.g., based on the name of the workflow, the PID of measuring devices, involved researchers/operators).

As pointed out above, we have been and still are in constant communication with other projects and working groups at GFZ. We also presented BPMN4Earth during a weekly seminar at GFZ, had a poster at the NFDI4Earth Plenary in 2024, and supported Daniel Funk with an article for an online publishing platform (Funk, 2025), but with regards to WP6 (“Publication and outreach”), we have fallen short of our own expectations so far. We expect a number of future publications though, especially in the context of Sematic x-Lab.

V. Future Directions

To remedy the shortcomings of the current application and facilitate the integration of BPMN4Earth into Semantic x-Lab, we are going to migrate from the current CLI to SpiffArena’s

⁴We are using the ACM definition for the terms repeatability (“same team, same experimental setup”) and replicability (“different team, same experimental setup”) (Association for Computing machinery, 2020).

GUI. In the course of the transition, it is likely that we will also discuss, if a RDF compatible format like RDF/XML, Turtle or JSON-LD should be favored over plain JSON for data exchange and workflow persistency, or if we should even switch to a graph database. The SpiffWorkflow community was indifferent towards this question, but within the context of Semantic x-Lab it might become more relevant.

Because we were quite aware of the limitations of the CLI application, we are still lacking proper documentation. We expect that a GUI version will be much more self-explanatory, but will address the issue after the transition as well. Moreover, we would like to utilize our experiences so far to create a BPMN workflow that helps users to create their own workflows. This would help to increase workflow quality and avoid common pitfalls.

Should the GitLab concept for PIDs prove to be feasible, we'll look for ways to integrate Zenodo with GitLab (similar to Zenodo's existing GitHub integration) to facilitate workflow publications. Because a lot of potential users probably won't be comfortable with GitLab, this would require a user-friendly integration into the GUI, though.

VI. References

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